

CLINICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CORONAVIRUS INFECTION (COVID-19) DURING DIABETES MELLITUS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12730443>

Global and domestic data indicate a higher mortality rate in patients with diabetes mellitus (DM) due to COVID-19, which determines the high relevance of the analysis of risk factors for adverse disease outcomes in DM to justify the management tactics of this category of patients.

Objective: to evaluate the effect of clinical and demographic parameters (age; gender; body mass index, BMI; glycemic control, HbA1c), as well as antidiabetic and antihypertensive drugs, including angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors and angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs), on clinical outcomes (recovery or death) in patients with Type 2 DM (SD2).

Materials and methods. A retrospective analysis of the database of the Federal Register of Diabetes Mellitus (RSD) was performed, which included patients with DM2 (n=309) with pneumonia/COVID-19 and the indicated disease outcome (recovery/death) in the period from 02/01/2020 to 04/27/2020.

Results. The mortality rate was 15.2% (47 out of 309 people). It was found that mortality was significantly higher in males (OR=2.08; 95% CI 1.1–3.9; p=0.022) and patients on insulin therapy (OR=2.67; 95% CI 1.42–5.02; p=0.002). Mortality was significantly lower in patients aged less than 65 years (OR=0.34; 95% CI 0.18–0.67; p=0.001); in patients receiving metformin (OR=0.26; 95% CI 0.14–0.5; p<0.0001), antihypertensive therapy in general (OR=0.43; 95% CI 0.22–0.82; p=0.009), beta blockers (OR=0.26; 95% CI 0.08–0.86; p=0.018), diuretics (OR=0.4; 95% CI 0.17–0.93; p=0.028) and blockers of the renin-angiotensin system (ACE or ARB) (OR=0.36; 95% CI 0.18–0.74; p=0.004). There was a tendency to increase mortality with higher HbA1c and BMI values, which did not reach statistical significance. Patients receiving insulin therapy differed from those without insulin therapy by a significantly longer duration of DM2 (13.4 vs. 6.8 years, p<0.0001), worse glycemic control in general (HbA1c 8.1 vs. 7.0%, p<0.0001) and 3 times more frequent failure to achieve the HbA1c goal by more than 2.5% (14.7 vs. 5.9%, p=0.04).

Conclusion. The identified risk factors for mortality in patients with DM2 indicate that good glycemic control, previous treatment with metformin and

antihypertensive drugs (including blockers of the renin-angiotensin system) can reduce the incidence of deaths. Higher mortality on insulin therapy was associated with poorer glycemic control in this group of patients.

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